

The FOCSI Program uses NDI to reduce risk and cost.

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Abstract.

FOCSI is a showcase example of a state-of-the-art (high tech) system development that utilized NDI technologies from DoD and industry to achieve the final performance goal. One of the major problems and technical risk areas that confronted the engineers at both McDonnell Aircraft Company and General Electric was packaging of the optical technology utilized on the FOCSI program. Extensive use was made of packaging technologies developed by the Navy's Advanced Avionics Technology Demonstration (AATD) Program and Standard Hardware Acquisition and Reliability Program (SHARP). Since modularity was preferred, these technologies reduced cost by an estimated \$3,100,000. This approach allowed McDonnell Aircraft Company, General Electric, and their subcontractors to concentrate on unsolved technical problems.

Background.

The fiber optic control system integration (FOCSI) Program is primarily sponsored by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the Navy, through the Naval Air Systems Command (NAVAIR). The goal of the program is to develop and test several optical sensors for aircraft flight control and engine control. Evaluation of fiber optic termini and the MIL-STD-1773 fiber optic data bus will also be achieved. The two prime contractors are McDonnell Aircraft Company (for the flight control effort) and General Electric (for the engine control effort). This paper will concentrate on the flight control effort, noting that the engine control system is similar. Flight testing is scheduled to begin December 1992 on an F-18 at NASA Dryden Flight Research Center.

The flight control effort includes the development and evaluation of 10 optical sensors that represent a wide range of sensor types

required for flight control. Figure 1 indicates the various sensors, sensor vendors, and location on the test aircraft. The sensor interface is indicated as the electro-optic architecture (EOA) indicated. A complete system block diagram is provided in figure 2, with interfaces from and to both the flight control EOA and the engine control EOA. Optical data interfaces are highlighted, as well as the MIL-STD-1773 optical data bus. It should be noted that the flight control EOA is an integration of both modules from Litton Poly-Scientific and McDonnell Aircraft Company by McDonnell Aircraft and is depicted in figure 3. This subsystem will be discussed in terms of the nondevelopment Items NDI utilized, specifically those developed under Navy-sponsored programs.

Summary.

One of the major problems and technical risk areas that confronted the engineers at both McDonnell Aircraft Company and General Electric was packaging of the optical technology utilized on the FOCSI program. This included environmental considerations and interfaces at the sensors and at the EOA units. Extensive use was made of packaging technologies developed by the Navy's Advanced Avionics Technology Demonstration (AATD) Program and Standard Hardware Acquisition and Reliability Program (SHARP). Since modularity was preferred, these technologies reduced technical risk as well as reduced cost by an estimated \$3,100,000. All NDI technologies used were concentrated within the EOA units and include standard processor modules, standard power supplies, standard enclosures, blind mate optic termini, and MIL-STD-1773 conversion hardware.

These enabling technologies allowed the contractors to concentrate efforts on other technical risk areas that had not been previously demonstrated, and to construct modular flight quality hardware integrating optics. Each product is discussed with concentration on optical technologies.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

OPTICAL TERMINI

The optical termini selected for both EOA units is a 20 gauge lens termini manufactured by G & H Technologies developed under a Navy contract. This termini is compatible with 150, 250, and 396 pin connectors available as military components per MIL-C-28754. The termini have slightly more loss than butt termini. However, when loss budgets allow, the ease of application is desirable. These lense termini do not require an interface pressure like the butt type, and they are more tolerant to foreign debris. This made their application to the FOCSI modules low risk since prior technical demonstration and testing had been performed on Standard Electronic Module (SEM) format E samples. McDonnell Aircraft is constructing a backplane that utilizes G & H lens termini and optic fiber that is exposed and suspended over the electrical contact pins. This technique for backplane fiber management was previously demonstrated which presented a low risk approach. See figure 4 for assembly of fiber on the backplane. Optical and printed wiring board process engineers at NAWC Indianapolis are pursuing a parallel effort that embeds the optical fiber in a printed wiring board backplane. If this approach proves successful, it will be used in the flight testing. The embedded fiber backplane effort will utilize and demonstrate tight bend optical fiber and low profile (miniaturized) lensed optical termini.

MIL-STD-1773 OPTICAL DATA BUS

The MIL-STD-1773 data bus is being implemented through conversion of MIL-STD-1553B electrical signals to optical signals. This approach has been demonstrated by using only an optical emitter and detector connected to the electrical bus. However, the technique being used for the conversion allows for multiple terminal connection to the optical bus which cannot be accomplished with previous implementations. The new technique requires encoding the MIL-STD-1553B signals to 8 MHz using Manchester coding circuitry. This allows all data on the optical bus to be exchanged at 8 MHz. Decoders connected to the optical bus can discriminate between converted MIL-STD-1553B signals and others by the length of the start bit. This feature allows for forward compatibility with faster implementations of MIL-STD-1773, while being backward compatible with MIL-STD-1553B. See figure 5 for specific electrical and optical waveforms. The type 1 signal indicated in figure 5 is representative of the optical signal.

Technology utilized on the converter module include the G & H lensed termini, new optical receivers with -40 dBm sensitivity and 26 dBm dynamic range and BICMOS gate arrays clocked at 64 MHz, implementing encoding and decoding state machines.

The optical data bus was demonstrated in the fall of 1991 at NAWC Indianapolis with four nodes connected to a 4x4 optical coupler. This was a true bus demonstration where optical transmitters and receivers were linked via the coupler. Due to the low sensitivity of the receivers, it was not necessary to utilize an active coupler, and a passive star coupler was used. Figure 6 is a photograph of the demonstration system. The current module design has been tested and determined to have a bit error rate of 1 in 10 billion which is acceptable for avionics data bus application.

STANDARD NDI

It is significant to note that standard products were also used extensively in the EOA's. A MIL-STD-1750A processor module which is NDI was used in three subsystems as a controller and coordinator of MIL-STD-1553B message traffic. Referencing figure 2, two are used in the airframe EOA as the CPU/1553 RT module and the 1553 controller module. Also in the engine EOA, one is used as the 1553 bus interface module. It is significant that multiple contractors used the same NDI hardware which reduced possible design redundancy. This obviously reduced technical risk, as well as saved money.

Figure 4

Figure 5

MIL-STD-1553B To MIL-STD-1773
Converter Module in 4-Node Optical Network

Figure 6

McDonnell Aircraft Company utilized a standard 3/4 air transport rack ATR enclosure which was previously tested in avionics environments. They were concerned about radiated electro-magnetic interference EMI susceptibility, and the existing test data and design data provided a starting foundation for the airframe EOA enclosure.

Finally, McDonnell Aircraft Company, with Navy funding, incorporated a SEM E power supply purchased from Texas Instruments. This power supply was an NDI product that was adopted by SHARP to align with the SEM E standard. McDonnell Aircraft had alternate power supply options and had not intended to develop a power supply for FOCSI. Therefore, the use of this NDI product cannot attribute to development cost savings.

Conclusion.

FOCSI is a showcase example of a state-of-the-art (high tech) system development that utilized NDI technologies from DoD and industry to achieve the final performance goal. This approach allowed McDonnell Aircraft Company, General Electric, and their subcontractors to concentrate on unsolved technical problems. While lowering cost and reducing risk for the contractors, as well as the government agencies involved.